

MOIN4Herbie deliverable 8 - Herbie protocols (backend and frontend) developed from ontologies

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Figure 1: MOIN4Herbie logo

Introduction

Purpose of this document

This document contains deliverable #8 *Herbie protocols (backend and frontend) developed from ontologies* of the project MOIN4Herbie - Maintenance Ontology and audit log Integration for Herbie funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). Deliverable #8 is part of work package 3 *Integration of maintenance ontologies in Herbie*. In this document, our approach to developing Herbie protocols, both backend and frontend, from the MOIN ontology is described.

Herbie electronic lab notebook

Herbie is an electronic lab notebook platform built on a collaborative knowledge graph system, which uses an RDF triple store with features like versioning and access control. Users can upload RDF data, including vocabularies and SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) shapes for data validation.

The MOIN4Herbie project focuses specifically on storing sensor maintenance metadata within Herbie. To enable this, ontologies specific to sensor maintenance were developed.

MOIN ontology

The Maintenance Ontology and audit log INtegration (MOIN) Ontology is a newly developed ontology designed to describe sensor maintenance tasks within a research context. It builds upon several pre-existing ontologies, including the Semantic Sensor Network Ontology and PROV-O: The PROV Ontology. MOIN encompasses all relevant actors involved in sensor maintenance, such as the sensors themselves, the platforms they are located on, and the personnel responsible for carrying out maintenance. Additionally, it outlines maintenance tasks like calibration and cleaning in general terms, as these tasks vary depending on the specific sensor and the standard operating procedures of the sensor platform.

SHACL:

SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) is a W3C standard used to validate RDF (Resource Description Framework) data. It allows us to define rules, called “shapes”, that describe how data should be structured, such as required properties (e.g., every Sensor must have a `hasLocation`), value types (e.g., `hasTimestamp` must be an `xsd:dateTime`), and cardinality (e.g., exactly one `hasID` per Instrument). SHACL helps ensure data quality and consistency in semantic web and linked data applications by enabling automated checks against these constraints.

SHACL in Herbie:

The integration of SHACL in Herbie enables the generation of user-friendly web forms that collect, validate, and provision FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data using RDF graphs. SHACL enables ontology-guided data entry, ensuring that the resulting metadata is fully aligned with FAIR principles.

The users can enter all metadata on their maintenance in customized web forms. And once submitted, Herbie automatically adds semantic annotations and stores everything directly in the knowledge graph. So, it is as easy to use as a spreadsheet but produces FAIR data without any additional post-processing work.

Approach

Create SHACL shapes

To create customized web forms for the users (the frontend implementation of Herbie), we are creating SHACL shapes for each step of the sensor maintenance, which corresponds to a web form.

Some tasks are generic, such as creating the basic information needed to fill in more complex tasks. This includes for example: - Defining a person who can carry out a task - Describing a feature of interest, in which the sensors operate - Describing cleaning material - Adding a sampler used in sampling processes - Creating a maintenance plan and assigning steps to it

For each of these tasks, a specific SHACL shape, corresponding in the frontend to a user form, is generated.

Example SHACL shape for a basic sampler

```
#IRI of this shape
@prefix : <http://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/moin/shapes/sampler/#> .
#Imported ontologies
@prefix hash: <http://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/herbie/hash/#> .
@prefix moin: <http://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/moin/#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix terms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix vann: <http://purl.org/vocab/vann/> .

#Definition of this shape
<> a owl:Ontology ;
  #versioned IRI
  owl:versionIRI <http://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/moin/shapes/sampler/1.0.0/> ;
  owl:versionInfo "1.0.0" ;
  owl:imports <http://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/moin/1.0.0/> ;
  #Label
  rdfs:label "The sampler SHACL shapes for MOIN"@en ;
  #Comment
  rdfs:comment "This document contains SHACL shapes which define an input form for a sampler" ;
  #Authors
  terms:creator "Catriona Eschke", "Fabian Kirchner", "Linda Baldewein", "Smruthishree Srinivasan" ;
  #Prefix of this shape
  vann:preferredNamespacePrefix "sampler" ;
.
```

```

#Sampler Shape
#NodeShape = Main wrapper of all the fields displayed in this form
:SamplerShape a sh:NodeShape ;
  #targetClass in ontology to which everything in this shape is connected
  sh:targetClass moin:Sampler ;
  hash:documentRoot true ;
  #connection to Annotation Property to add information to our sampler
  sh:property :SamplerShape_rdfsLabel ;
.

:SamplerShape_rdfsLabel a sh:PropertyShape ;
  #path to annotation property to label the sampler
  sh:path rdfs:label ;
  #Defining the input as a string
  sh:datatype xsd:string ;
  #Making input mandatory
  sh:minCount 1 ;
  sh:maxCount 1 ;
  #Giving the field in the form a name
  sh:name "sampler name"@en ;
.

```

The form will be rendered in Herbie as a simple text field to input a name:

Creating more complex input forms necessitates the use of more intricate SHACL shapes.

Application specific ontology MOIN4BoknisEck

In this project, the Herbie ELN was utilized to support the digital recording of sensor maintenance metadata for two specific use cases: Tesperhude and Boknis Eck.

Based on interactions with sensor owners and managers, it became clear that sensor maintenance procedures can vary significantly depending on several factors, including sensor type, manufacturer, model, environmental conditions, and the operational protocols defined by the owning organization. For instance, at the Boknis Eck site, a specific four-step calibration procedure must be followed for calibrating an oxygen optode. This procedure requires the storage of five distinct parameters in Herbie.

By default, the Herbie would only provide a single field for entering calibration values, which is insufficient for capturing the complete procedure. If these additional parameters are recorded in a general comments section instead, the resulting metadata becomes non-queryable and, consequently, less useful for structured data analysis.

To address this limitation, customized web forms were developed for each use case. These forms were built using task-specific ontologies, in this case MOIN4BoknisEck, enabling structured, queryable, and semantically rich metadata capture aligned with the specific calibration procedures and sensor types in use.

RO-Crate

RO-Crate (Research Object Crate) is a community-driven, lightweight framework for packaging research data together with rich metadata in a structured and machine-readable format. It uses JSON-LD and builds on schema.org annotations.

Importing RO-Crate in Herbie

1. To access the Herbie ELN, open a web browser and navigate to the Herbie portal at: <https://herbie.hereon.de/>.
2. After logging into Herbie, select the workspace in which you would like to work. If you are using Herbie for the first time, create a new workspace by providing a name and description.
3. Once the workspace is selected, click on **Documents** from the left-hand navigation panel.
4. Next, click the **+** **button** located in the top-left corner. This button provides options to create a new document, import a graph, or import an RO-Crate into Herbie.
5. Select the **Import RO-Crate** option, then browse to the directory where the **.zip** archive of the RO-Crate is stored. Choose the archive file you wish to import into Herbie. For testing the MOIN ontology implementation in forms, you can use the provided RO-Crate.
6. After initiating the import, the **RO-Crate Imports** window will appear. It will initially display the status as **“Processing...”** for the selected RO-Crate.
7. Once the import process is complete, the status will change to either **“Successful”** if the RO-Crate was imported correctly, or **“Failed”** if there was an issue during import.
8. After a successful import, the SHACL shapes contained in the RO-Crate will become available. To access them, click the **+** **button** again in the

Figure 2: Opening the import RO-Crate window

RO-Crate Imports

by	Uploaded at	Finished at	Took s	Status
hia	6/26/2025, 2:26 PM			Processing...
hia	6/20/2025, 4:18 PM	6/20/2025, 4:18 PM	41	Successful
hia	6/20/2025, 4:11 PM	6/20/2025, 4:12 PM	55	Successful
hia	6/20/2025, 4:00 PM	6/20/2025, 4:01 PM	66	Successful
hia	6/20/2025, 3:57 PM	6/20/2025, 3:58 PM	40	Successful

Figure 3: uploading an RO-Crate

top-left corner and select **Document**, which opens the **Create Document** window where the imported shapes can now be used.

Discussion and conclusion

SHACL shapes are the frontend and backend protocols used by Herbie to render user forms. Within the MOIN4Herbie project, we developed a series of SHACL shapes to display both generic and task specific web forms.

On the frontend, it guides dynamic, ontology-based forms that simplify data entry for our scientists/users. On the backend, it validates that the metadata aligns with top level ontology MOIN and application ontology MOIN4BoknisEck, ensuring consistency, machine-readability, and FAIR compliance.

As each specific task requires its own SHACL shape, the MOIN4Herbie team will continue to develop more SHACL shapes throughout the project runtime.

A functioning core, however is already accessible at the public repository for MOIN4Herbie. Using the RO-crate, anyone can test the shapes in the publicly accessible Herbie instance.